

Hoax behavior tendencies among Indonesian students: An analysis during the COVID-19 pandemic

Afdal Afdal^{1,3}, Miftahul Fikri¹, Neviyarni Neviyarni¹, Mega Iswari¹, Indah Sukmawati¹, Firman Firman¹, Yeni Karneli¹, Mardianto Mardianto^{2,3}, Rezki Hariko^{1,3}

¹Department Guidance and Counseling, Faculty of Education, Universitas Negeri Padang, Padang, Indonesia

²Faculty of Psychology and Health, Universitas Negeri Padang, Padang, Indonesia

³Cyberpsychology Intervention and Research Centre, Universitas Negeri Padang, Padang, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Jan 5, 2022

Revised Oct 14, 2022

Accepted Nov 7, 2022

Keywords:

Counseling

COVID-19 pandemic

Hoax behavior tendency

Student

ABSTRACT

The objective of this study was to analyze the hoax behavior tendencies among Indonesian students during the pandemic, viewed from the aspects of analytical thinking, basic science knowledge, trust in news sources, satisfaction, and action. A total of 633 male and female students from Indonesian universities were sampled used a simple random sampling technique. Data were collected through the hoax tendency behavior scale (HTBS) on 30 questions using a Likert scale. Then, the data were analyzed descriptively to evaluate the hoax behavior tendencies in adolescents during the pandemic, which the results revealed to be in the medium category. Therefore, the analytical thinking skills of adolescents need to be improved, as 31.75% and 2.53% were in the low and very low categories. The study showed that adolescents with an average age of 20 years spreading hoaxes were motivated by basic knowledge of science, trust in news sources, satisfaction, and action. However, there was no significant influence of gender, parental income, and areas of residence, such as rural, urban, and suburban, on those that exhibit hoax behaviors.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Afdal

Department Guidance and Counseling, Faculty of Education, Universitas Negeri Padang
Padang, West Sumatera, Indonesia

Email: afdal@konselor.org; afdal.kons@fip.unp.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

The new outbreak called coronavirus disease-19 (COVID-19), which originated from Wuhan, China [1]–[6], was declared a global pandemic and resulted in thousands of deaths in 216 countries [7], including Indonesia [8]. Hence, this situation has become the focus of the today world's attention. Individual responses while facing the COVID-19 situation are very diverse, depending on their perceptions and processing of available information [9], and many people downplay the danger of the pandemic [10], [11]. Attitude denial or underestimation of the disease influences a person's judgment, perception [12] and behaviors [13]. Nevertheless, they must still follow the government rules of handwashing, social distancing [14], and facemask use [15]. Explained that various forms of belief are positively correlated with different behaviors. For instance, confidence develops in stressed or critical situations [16]. Furthermore, doubts or a lack of conviction are caused by the inability to obtain accurate information regarding the current pandemic, alongside the deployment through mass media, especially social media, among adolescents [17]–[20]. However, the acquisition of information via print publications is less attractive to people that have started to depend on accessibility through the internet [19], [21]–[26].

Social media can be categorized based on four considerations: i) The capacity to influence virtually all aspects of community life; ii) The ability to reach many people from different classes; iii) The possibility of using various features of the new media, such as internet premises and rapid transmission process; iv) The involvement of all social media aspects, including the role as a communicator and communicant, interacting simultaneously in the same space and time [27], [28]. Therefore, social media is an important medium because its presence has exerted a great influence on the delivery of messages. Currently, communication is performed more often through the internet [25], [29], [30]. The role of social media in public has also improved, stimulating recent research, health care in education, directing people to websites and landing pages for reliable information on the latest health advances, and marketing innovative services such as social fund services and related posts. Consequently, the provision of permitted case information, photos, and results, alongside the communication of reviews and testimonials of recovered patients, offer support among Indonesian citizens during the COVID-19 pandemic [31].

The development of the internet and information technology directly affects humans' basic needs, and the rapid, precise, and accurate acquisition of information plays an important role in many aspects of life. However, the comfort and convenience offered in the information age also invite acts of crime or criminality in cyberspace [32], such as hoaxes [33]–[39]. Despite the efforts of social media to limit its spread [40], [41], hoaxes are difficult to contain, leading to increasing popularity and massive circulation of the term. Many people are tricked into believing false news on social media and often do not realize their role in the spread. Since the COVID-19 outbreak, the crux of the misleading information circulated is the assumption that the virus and symptoms are fake, leading to problems concerning the government policies in each country. The spread of false information or hoaxes related to this pandemic is not limited to Indonesia but occurs in other countries [15], [42]–[44]. Generally, social media plays similar but more extensive roles than the old media in conveying or misinforming the public about the virus [15], [38], [43]–[48]. The predominant means of spreading hoaxes was social media, such as Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. Chat applications, such as WhatsApp, Line, and Telegram, are also phenomenal in disseminating false information, and approximately 60.80% of the public use applications to spread hoaxes [28]. Encountering hoaxes is an implication of the massive use of electronic technology, especially information and communication. Social media enables receiving, sharing, as well as commenting on issues, meanwhile overlapping, implosive, and explosive information are reproduced through share and copy options available on the platform's system. Hence, people can comment on received information without confirmation, causing social media to become a virtual trend for today's society. Besides being a communication medium, it has developed into a means of sharing information or responding to trending issues in cyberspace [49]–[53].

Meanwhile, information and communication technology (ICT) are currently evolving with various media, including online systems. The ease and efficiency offered by online media facilitate its application for disseminating influential information to the community. It has also changed the way messages are conveyed and consumed. Currently, dissemination is not solely performed through online media by known news sites but also other people that use the internet. This has led to the irresponsible distribution of news individually or in groups, making the discovery of accurate information difficult [54]–[59]. Although the positive effect of ICT development on humans cannot be denied [26], [60]–[62], the latent negative effects, especially in the social networking aspect, are troubling. This is majorly due to hoaxes or false information spread on social media about an uncertain or unclarified fact, occurrence, or source. Consequently, the information can lead to the interpretation desired by interested persons. Hoaxes are booming in this current information age, and their existence majorly impacts various aspects, especially supported by the people's increased use of the internet for accessing social networks and instant messaging [63], [64]. Furthermore, the circulation of negative news and hoaxes among the public leads to many dangers, including causing inciting people's emotions, division of society, provocation, and the spread of animosity, anger, and hate speech [24], [39].

Hoaxes are more prevalent in cyberspace than broadcast media, such as television, and are easy to spread and attract followers for at least three reasons. First, the virtual world, indicated by the existence of social media, provides freedom of accessibility without restrictions or complicated rules as in society. Second, broadcasting media, such as television, are mostly controlled by people or groups with political tendencies, and third, hoax booms are determined or even supported by the increasing number of internet users. Consequently, this phenomenon is causing various problems in Indonesia [34], [49], [50], [65], [66], as the people are also prone to sharing false news. This is obvious from the existence of about 170 million Indonesians, who own at least one cellphone or SIM card [67]. The spread of hoaxes is very worrying [68], [69] and should not be disregarded because it can be penalized by law [25]. Generally, hoaxes are created intentionally for jokes, fun, to form a public opinion, and gain profits based on the number of people that access and share the news through various other media [14], [19], [33]–[35], [70]–[74]. The increase in hoaxes regarding the COVID-19 pandemic is an important problem in society presently, and persons that do not abuse social media for personal gain are also likely to spread false.

In Indonesia, the presence of social media influences political, social, cultural, and economic changes. Social media shifts and penetrates boundaries from hierarchical interaction patterns in political and cultural spaces to become egalitarian, influencing everyone who reads hoax news [35], [37], [66]. Facts show that the rapid spread of hoaxes comes from reliable information, resulting in a very complex problem [37], [75], [76]. Many people are getting active access to COVID-19 and health-related information during this pandemic period, causing increased anxiety levels due to the incorrect information from social media [70], [71], [73]. This affects the government's ability to reduce illness and death from the disease due to people's wrong beliefs about the virus [14], [77]. Belief in information circulating through the media makes users vulnerable to hoaxes and affects their perceptions and behavior. An interesting finding showed that people look for more information on the internet or social media [78]–[80]. However, such information could trigger feelings of anxiety especially in the millennial generation, indicating exposure to hoaxes.

The issue of COVID-19 is circulating and troubling the public, and the fake information related to this disease on social media is often found associated with political issues. Meanwhile, the progress of the modern era can positively and negatively impact the development of adolescents. Individuals generally face many stressful events daily during adolescence. Also, teenagers in the millennial era are very attached to their gadgets, which are a means used to facilitate coping or release from stress. Information hoaxes spread to the millennial generation requires significant vigilance to prevent their interference with societal stability. In this case, adolescents that possess confidence in their abilities and develop positive personal and environmental assessments can face issues calmly including responses to hoax information about COVID-19. A person is judged to have good literacy about this disease by possessing adequate knowledge, behavior, and positive actions regarding the spread of hoaxes. Consequently, this research study will analyze trends in hoax behavior among adolescents during the COVID-19 pandemic. The importance of understanding and reviewing information circulating through social media is to decrease the level of hoaxes concerning the pandemic to avoid harming the community, alongside reduce the intensity of COVID-19 exposure.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This study was conducted using a quantitative descriptive method to analyze hoax behavior tendencies in adolescents concerning the COVID-19 pandemic. A total of 633 students comprising male and female university students were selected by simple random sampling. Data were collected through the hoax tendency behavior scale (HTBS) on 30 question items using a Likert scale. The data employed descriptive analysis consisting of five aspects, including analytical thinking ability, basic science knowledge, and action (the tendency to spread) with six items each, alongside trust in news sources and satisfaction with the hoax news, with five and seven, respectively. Instrument validation using Rasch analysis shows that the overall instrument used is valid and reliable (person reliability is 0.83 and item reliability is 1.00) [81].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The hoax behavior tendencies based on the domains revealed by the HTBS on Indonesian students are presented in Table 1. The table shows that the dominant misbehavior from all aspects occurred in the medium category with overall maximum (highest) and minimum (lowest) scores of 127 and 40, respectively, an 80.23 average and a standard deviation of 14.47. These findings obtained from the analysis of each aspect, the tendency to behave based on hoaxes is in the medium category.

Table 1. Description of the behavior trends according to hoaxes using sub-variables (N=633)

No	Aspect	Ideal	Max	Min	Mean	SD	Category (%)				
							Very high	High	Medium	Low	Very low
1	Analytical thinking ability	30	26	8	16.82	3.20	0.47	11.69	53.55	31.75	2.53
2	Basic science knowledge	30	29	6	16.18	3.54	0.16	9.32	50.24	33.97	6.32
3	Trust in News Sources	25	24	5	13.26	3.26	0	3.48	40.60	45.97	9.95
4	Satisfaction	35	31	7	19.4	4.07	0	2.52	39.94	50.31	6.76
5	Action	30	26	6	13.86	3.86	0.16	4.11	28.28	45.18	22.27
	Total	150	127	40	80.23	14.47	0.16	6.16	51.34	39.34	3.00

The ability to think analytically produced an average score of 16.82 and 53.55% in the medium category, meaning that a person's analytical thinking ability is sufficient to contribute to the tendency to exhibit hoax behaviors. Meanwhile, the basic science knowledge aspect had an average score of 16.18 as well 50.24% in the medium category, denoting that a person's knowledge base moderately influences their tendency to behave according to hoaxes. The trust in news sources aspect generated an average of 13.26 and

a 45.97% score in the low category (L), meaning the variable did not affect this tendency. Furthermore, the satisfaction aspect obtained an average of 19.4 and a 50.31% score in the low category (L), signifying that satisfaction influences hoaxes and a decrease result in reduced misbehavior tendencies. The last aspect was action, which had a 13.86 average and a 45.18% score in the low category (L), meaning that a lack of contributed action to the tendency to behave to hoax. Consequently, these results show that the analytical thinking abilities of adolescents need to be improved, as 31.75% and 2.53% were in the low and very low categories, respectively. Likewise, the basic science knowledge, trust in news sources, satisfaction, and action should be enhanced, as many teenagers spread hoaxes. Therefore, all the aspects contributed to an increase in hoax behavior tendencies in adolescents.

Generally, mastery of science and higher-level thinking capabilities are required to attain thought competence [82]. Thinking skills are very important [83], [84] and are needed alongside a conscious and tech-savvy attitude [85]–[87]. The ability to think is an awareness existing in a person that cannot be observed directly [88]. It ensures that individuals can have opinions in solving problems and analyze received information by first guessing, investigating, and then describing the subject of the problem. The ability to think analytically allows the provision of solutions to problems, which is one of the higher-order thinking skills that facilitate independence in individuals. Meanwhile, an understanding or mastery of the concepts related to the problem to be solved supports this analytical thinking ability and is an important asset in determining strategies [89]–[91]. This ability is therefore important against the spread of hoaxes concerning the COVID-19 pandemic. Fake news, also known as hoaxes [68], [92], [93] refers to information that is added or subtracted from the actual event or content and involves aspects of manipulation or modification to achieve various responses [42]. Therefore, the capacity of processing information individually is very influential during the emergence of hoaxes [64], [94]. There are two triggers or motives for hoax information, namely economic and political. For instance, sensational news is deliberately displayed on sites to obtain numerous visits, while the motives of others are to channel political aspirations through social media by creating fake news [58], [71], [95], [96]. Hoaxes that cause various physical and mental health problems can be found on social media [55], [63], [97]. Such news creates collective panic or fear [48], [95] and leads to behaviors [71], that vary according to internal stimuli, including knowledge, attitudes, facilities, experience, culture, society, and beliefs. Table 2 shows the contribution of each sub-variable.

Table 2. Results of the simple linear regression analysis based on the tendency to behave according to hoaxes

Aspect	ATA	BSK	TiNS	S	A	HBT
Analytical thinking ability (ATA)		.308	.244	.391	.330	.635
Basic science knowledge (BSK)	.308		.366	.247	.217	.588
Trust in news sources (TiNS)	.244	.366		.302	.251	.593
Satisfaction (S)	.391	.247	.302		.549	.743
Action (A)	.330	.217	.251	.549		.686
Hoax behavior tendencies (HBT)	.635	.588	.593	.743	.686	

As shown in Table 2, the predisposition to exhibiting hoax behavior tendencies based on the contribution of the action sub-variable to satisfaction amounted to 54.9%, while 45.1% was influenced by other factors. Likewise, the hoax behavior tendencies influenced the satisfaction variable by 74.3%, while 25.7% was caused by other factors. The findings in this study show that higher satisfaction obtained from the hoax behavior tendencies resulted in increased action. However, basic science knowledge had the lowest contribution of 21.7% to the action aspect, meaning even a little scientific information leads to a reduction in this tendency. In addition, the influence of trust in the news sources on the analytical thinking ability was 24.4%, signifying that a small percentage of trust in information sources results in a tendency to misbehave. Hence, this study shows that the tendency to behave based on a hoax is mostly caused by satisfaction, while even small levels of basic science knowledge had an inverse effect.

Also, the hoax behavior tendencies produced scores of 74.3% and 58.8% for satisfaction and basic science knowledge respectively. This shows that high basic science knowledge will decrease the tendency and low satisfaction enhances this predisposition. The results revealed that hoax behavior tendencies are mostly caused by satisfaction and action, as shown by scores of 74.3% and 68.6%, followed by trust in news sources at 59.3%, and the analytical thinking ability at 63.5%. Therefore, the aspects regarding the tendency to behave based on hoaxes, which had the highest or dominant interconnection were satisfaction and action. Conversely, the least dominant was the influence of basic science knowledge on the action variable, followed by the effect of trust in news sources on analytical thinking ability. Meanwhile, there was no significant difference between men's and women's tendency to misbehave, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3 shows that the group statistics in this study comprised 118 males and 515 females. The average or mean value for the males was 82.40 and 79.74 for females, showing a difference in the tendency of hoax-driven behaviors based on gender. Table 4 presents the interpretation of the independent samples t-tests to determine the significance of the difference.

Table 3. Description of gender data based on the hoax behavior tendencies

Gender	N	Group statistics			
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	
HBT	Male	118	82.40	16.462	1.515
	Female	515	79.74	13.946	.615

Table 4. Results of t-test analysis in terms of gender

		Levene's test for equality of variances			t-test for equality of means					
		F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean difference	Std. error difference	95% confidence interval of the difference	
								Lower		Upper
HBT	Equal variances assumed	6.479	.11	1.805	631	.072	2.660	1.474	-.235	5.556
	Equal variances not assumed			1.627	157.671	.106	2.660	1.635	-.569	5.890

According to Table 4, the value of sig. Levene's test for equality of variances was $0.11 > 0.05$, meaning the data variance between male and female was homogeneous or the same. Also, independent sample t-test revealed a significance value of $0.072 > 0.05$, denoting the absence of a difference in the point scores. This means there is no significant difference between the trend of hoax behavior in men and female. The dissemination of misleading information in this pandemic can increase anxiety, suffering from paranoid, and health panics that can be observed through various symptoms. These include exaggerated maladaptive and logistical behaviors, avoiding medical treatment in hospitals, and distrust towards public authorities [98]. Therefore, the effects and types of hoaxes must be reviewed, and an accurate intervention level [99], [100].

4. CONCLUSION

This study showed that the tendency of hoax behaviors in student was in the medium category. Hence, their analytical thinking skills need to be improved, as 31.75% and 2.53% of the participants were in the low and very low categories. Likewise, basic science knowledge, trust in news sources, satisfaction, and action should be enhanced in teenagers that spread hoaxes. The dominant factor with the highest score that was closely linked to hoax behavior tendency was satisfaction at 74.3%, followed by action at 68.6%. Conversely, the lowest percentage and least dominant factor was the influence of basic science knowledge on the action variable at 21.7%, followed by the belief in news sources on the ability to think analytically at 24.4%. Hence, low levels of these aspects encourage people to behave according to hoaxes, while high levels will trigger a decrease in this tendency. This study also showed no significant influence of gender on adolescents' tendencies to misbehave due to hoaxes. Nevertheless, the creation of awareness, which can decrease these dangers, is the responsibility of all parties, especially education providers and parents. The role of educators, such as counselors, can help adolescents through the provision of various psychological interventions through guidance and counseling services and approaches. Likewise, future study should exploit social media as a means to impart literacy in students and encourage their analysis of the news spread throughout social media. Such actions are important, considering threatening news and hoaxes are a common threat, particularly for the millennial generation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful to everyone that partook in the research, including the respondents, research team, and the counselors in Indonesia for their support in achieving the objectives of the research and thank to *Lembaga Penelitian dan Pengabdian Masyarakat (LP2M) Universitas Negeri Padang* and Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology Republic of Indonesia for funding this work with a contract number: 238/UN.35/LT/2022.

REFERENCES

- [1] Z. J. Cheng, "2019 Novel coronavirus: where we are and what we know," *Infection*, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 155–163, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s15010-020-01401-y.
- [2] N. Fadakar, "A first case of acute cerebellitis associated with coronavirus disease (COVID-19): a case report and literature review," *Cerebellum*, vol. 19, no. 6, pp. 911–914, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s12311-020-01177-9.
- [3] T. Singhal, "A Review of coronavirus disease-2019 (COVID-19)," *Indian Journal of Pediatrics*, vol. 87, no. 4, pp. 281–286, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s12098-020-03263-6.
- [4] M. Rafiee, "A review on applicable and available paraclinical methods for diagnosis of coronavirus disease-19," *Archives of Iranian Medicine*, vol. 23, no. 11, pp. 794–800, 2020, doi: 10.34172/AIM.2020.106.
- [5] J. L. Santarpia, "Aerosol and surface contamination of SARS-CoV-2 observed in quarantine and isolation care," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 10, no. 1, 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41598-020-69286-3.
- [6] S. Kunal, "Cardiovascular system and COVID-19: Perspectives from a developing country," *Monaldi Archives for Chest Disease*, vol. 90, no. 2, pp. 231–241, 2020, doi: 10.4081/monaldi.2020.1305.
- [7] D. R. Sulistina, "Prevalence analysis of knowledge, perception, conspiracy, belief and acceptance of the COVID-19 vaccine in a global crossing study," *Science Midwifery*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 247–249, 2021.
- [8] I. Normalina, "Characterization of the spike glycoprotein and construction of an epitope-based vaccine candidate against Indonesian SARS-CoV-2: In silico study," *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*, vol. 11, no. 7, pp. 404–413, 2020, doi: 10.31838/srp.2020.7.60.
- [9] N. A. Pratama and D. Hidayat, "Community knowledge and behavior interpreting social distancing," *Journal Digital Media & Relationship*, vol. 2, no. 1, 2020.
- [10] D. K. D. Kim and G. L. Kreps, "An analysis of government communication in the United States during the COVID-19 pandemic: recommendations for effective government health risk communication," *World Medical & Health Policy*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 398–412, 2020, doi: 10.1002/wmh3.363.
- [11] X. Xiang *et al.*, "Modern senicide in the face of a pandemic: An examination of public discourse and sentiment about older adults and COVID-19 using machine learning," *The Journals of Gerontology: Series B*, vol. 76, no. 4, pp. e190–e200, 2021, doi: 10.1093/geronb/gbaa128.
- [12] X. Xie, "Generational differences in perceptions of food health/risk and attitudes toward organic food and game meat: The case of the COVID-19 crisis in China," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 17, no. 9, 2020, doi: 10.3390/ijerph17093148.
- [13] V. M. Cvetković, "Preparedness and preventive behaviors for a pandemic disaster caused by COVID-19 in Serbia," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 17, no. 11, pp. 1–23, 2020, doi: 10.3390/ijerph17114124.
- [14] M. L. Stanley, "Analytic-thinking predicts hoax beliefs and helping behaviors in response to the COVID-19 pandemic," *Thinking and Reasoning*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 464–477, 2021, doi: 10.1080/13546783.2020.1813806.
- [15] R. Imhoff, "A bioweapon or a hoax? the link between distinct conspiracy beliefs about the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) outbreak and pandemic behavior," *Social Psychological and Personality Science*, vol. 11, no. 8, pp. 1110–1118, 2020, doi: 10.1177/1948550620934692.
- [16] S. B. Bareeqa, "Prevalence of depression, anxiety and stress in china during COVID-19 pandemic: A systematic review with meta-analysis," *International Journal of Psychiatry in Medicine*, vol. 56, no. 4, pp. 210–227, 2021, doi: 10.1177/0091217420978005.
- [17] W. Efrizal, "Teenagers' perceptions and consumption patterns during the COVID-19 pandemic," *Ekotonia: Jurnal Penelitian Biologi, Botani, Zoologi dan Mikrobiologi*, vol. 05, no. 2, pp. 43–48, 2020.
- [18] The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health, "Pandemic school closures: risks and opportunities," *The Lancet Child and Adolescent Health*, vol. 4, no. 5, p. 341, 2020, doi: 10.1016/S2352-4642(20)30105-X.
- [19] R. K. Algethami, T. M. Alqarni, and F. M. a Albakour, "The effect of social media exposure on the mental health of individuals with disabilities during the coronavirus 2019 pandemic," *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 161–168, 2021, doi: 10.36941/jesr-2021-0086.
- [20] G. A. Priambodo, "The urgency of social media literacy in countering the threat of hoax news among teenagers," *Jurnal Civic Hukum*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 130–137, 2019.
- [21] D. Sarathchandra, "How believing climate change is a 'hoax' shapes climate skepticism in the United States," *Environmental Sociology*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 225–238, 2021, doi: 10.1080/23251042.2020.1855884.
- [22] E. H. Mahvelati, "Learners' perceptions and performance under peer versus teacher corrective feedback conditions," *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, vol. 70, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.stueduc.2021.100995.
- [23] M. Bruder, "The conspiracy hoax? Testing key hypotheses about the correlates of generic beliefs in conspiracy theories during the COVID-19 pandemic," *International Journal of Psychology*, 2021, doi: 10.1002/ijop.12769.
- [24] M. Keenan and K. Dillenburger, "How 'Fake News' affects autism policy," *Societies*, vol. 8, no. 2, p. 29, 2018, doi: 10.3390/soc8020029.
- [25] I. Santoso, I. Yohansen, N. Neelson, H. L. H. S. Warnars, and K. Hashimoto, "Early investigation of proposed hoax detection for decreasing hoax in social media," in *2017 IEEE International Conference on Cybernetics and Computational Intelligence (CyberneticsCom)*, 2018, vol. 2017, pp. 175–179, doi: 10.1109/CYBERNETICSCOM.2017.8311705.
- [26] M. Drouin, B. T. McDaniel, J. Pater, and T. Toscos, "How parents and their children used social media and technology at the beginning of the covid-19 pandemic and associations with anxiety," *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, vol. 23, no. 11, pp. 727–736, 2020, doi: 10.1089/cyber.2020.0284.
- [27] Alizamar, M. Fikri, Afdal, Y. Syahputra, I. Sukmawati, and A. Ilyas, "Phubbing behavior: How it's related to happiness," *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 348–358, 2019.
- [28] F. Fensi, "Hoax phenomenon: Challenges to media ideals & media ethics," (in Indonesian), *Bricolage*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 133–148, 2018, doi: 10.30813/bricolage.v4i02.1657.
- [29] R. Rodríguez-Ferrándiz, "Memetics of deception: Spreading local meme hoaxes during COVID-19 1st year," *Future Internet*, vol. 13, no. 6, 2021, doi: 10.3390/fi13060152.
- [30] Taufik, Alizamar, Afdal, M. Fikri, and I. Fidi, "Phubbing behaviour in Indonesian students," *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 263–272, 2019.
- [31] M. Mansoor, "Citizens' trust in government as a function of good governance and government agency's provision of quality information on social media during COVID-19," *Government Information Quarterly*, vol. 38, no. 4, p. 101597, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.giq.2021.101597.

- [32] N. A. R. Devi, "Efforts by the communication and informatics office (Diskominfo) in reducing the spread of fake news (Hoax) on online media in Samarinda," (in Indonesian), *eJournal Ilmu Pemerintahan*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1553–1566, 2019.
- [33] G. G. Cole, "Why the 'hoax' paper of baldwin (2018) should be reinstated," *Sociological Methods and Research*, vol. 50, no. 4, pp. 1895–1915, 2021, doi: 10.1177/0049124120914951.
- [34] T. Widaretna, "Hoax Identification on Tweets in Indonesia Using Doc2Vec," *2021 9th International Conference on Information and Communication Technology, ICoICT 2021*, 2021, pp. 456–461, doi: 10.1109/ICoICT52021.2021.9527515.
- [35] M. Rusli, "Types of covid-19 hoax in social media Indonesia," *Proceedings of the International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management*, 2021, pp. 4621–4629.
- [36] R. Adipradana, "Hoax analyzer for Indonesian news using rnns with fasttext and glove embeddings," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 2130–2136, 2021, doi: 10.11591/eei.v10i4.2956.
- [37] B. P. Nayoga, "Hoax analyzer for Indonesian news using deep learning models," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 179, pp. 704–712, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2021.01.059.
- [38] D. Varshney, "Hoax news-inspector: a real-time prediction of fake news using content resemblance over web search results for authenticating the credibility of news articles," *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, vol. 12, no. 9, pp. 8961–8974, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s12652-020-02698-1.
- [39] E. A. Jane, "'Dude ... stop the spread': antagonism, agonism, and #manspreading on social media," *International Journal of Cultural Studies*, vol. 20, no. 5, pp. 459–475, 2017, doi: 10.1177/1367877916637151.
- [40] C. Juditha, "Hoax communication interaction on social media and anticipation of hoax communication interactivity in social media and anticipation," *Jurnal Pekommas*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 31–44, 2018, di: 10.30818/jpkm.2018.2030104.
- [41] C. Juditha, "Community behavior related to the spread of hoax covid-19," *Jurnal Pekommas*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 105–116, 2020, doi: 10.30818/jpkm.2020.2050201.
- [42] H. Chumairoh, "The threat of fake news in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic," *Vox Populi*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 22–30, 2020, doi: 10.24252/vp.v3i1.14395.
- [43] R. Salaverría, "Disinformation in times of pandemic: Typology of hoaxes on Covid-19," *Profesional de la Informacion*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 1–15, 2020, doi: 10.3145/epi.2020.may.15.
- [44] C. Pérez-Curiel, "Impact of political discourse on the dissemination of hoaxes about covid-19. Influence of misinformation in public and media," *Revista Latina de Comunicacion Social*, vol. 2020, no. 78, pp. 65–97, 2020, doi: 10.4185/RLCS-2020-1469.
- [45] F. P. Rojano, "An anatomy of the electoral hoax: Political disinformation in Spain's 2019 general election campaign," *Revista CIDOB d'Afers Internacionals*, no. 124, pp. 123–145, 2020, doi: 10.24241/RCAI.2020.124.1.123.
- [46] O. Aiyewumi, "The myth that nigerians are immune to Sars-Cov-2 and that COVID-19 is a hoax are putting lives at risk," *Journal of Global Health*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 1–4, 2020, doi: 10.7189/jogh.10.020375.
- [47] M. Brüggemann, "Mutual group polarization in the blogosphere: tracking the hoax discourse on climate change," *International Journal of Communication*, vol. 14, pp. 1025–1048, 2020.
- [48] M. J. Ufarte-Ruiz, "Fact-checking, a public service value in the face of the hoaxes of the healthcare crisis," *Tripodos*, vol. 1, no. 47, pp. 87–104, 2020.
- [49] E. Oktaviansyah, "Predicting hoax spread in Indonesia using SIRS model," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1490, no. 1, 2020, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1490/1/012059.
- [50] A. S. Rustan, "Communication in Indonesian social media: Avoiding hate speeches, intolerance and hoax," *Journal of Social Studies Education Research*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 174–185, 2020.
- [51] S. Y. Yuliani, "Hoax news validation using similarity algorithms," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1524, no. 1, 2020, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1524/1/012035.
- [52] B. Zaman, "An Indonesian hoax news detection system using reader feedback and naïve bayes algorithm," *Cybernetics and Information Technologies*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 82–94, 2020, doi: 10.2478/cait-2020-0006.
- [53] M. P. Utami, "Hoax information detection system using apriori algorithm and random forest algorithm in Twitter," *6th International Conference on Interactive Digital Media, ICIDM 2020*, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ICIDM51048.2020.9339648.
- [54] K. Park, "Social media hoaxes, political ideology, and the role of issue confidence," *Telematics and Informatics*, vol. 36, pp. 1–11, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.tele.2018.11.001.
- [55] M. Sparke, "Reaction, resilience, and the trumpist behemoth: environmental risk management from 'hoax' to technique of domination," *Annals of the American Association of Geographers*, vol. 109, no. 2, pp. 533–544, 2019, doi: 10.1080/24694452.2018.1549469.
- [56] P. Assiroj, "Hoax news detection on social media: A Survey," *1st 2018 Indonesian Association for Pattern Recognition International Conference, INAPR 2018 - Proceedings*, 2019, pp. 186–191, doi: 10.1109/INAPR.2018.8627053.
- [57] A. P. Wijaya, "Improving the accuracy of naïve bayes algorithm for hoax classification using particle swarm optimization," *Proceedings - 2018 International Seminar on Application for Technology of Information and Communication: Creative Technology for Human Life, iSemantic 2018*, 2018, pp. 482–487, doi: 10.1109/ISEMANTIC.2018.8549700.
- [58] H. Prasetyono, "Character-based economic learning implementation and teacher's reinforcement on student's affective competence in minimizing hoax," *Cakrawala Pendidikan*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 426–435, 2018.
- [59] N. M. Huda, "The use of soft systems methodology to resolve Hoax news problems in Indonesia," *Proceedings - 2018 3rd International Conference on Information Technology, Information Systems and Electrical Engineering, ICITISEE 2018*, 2018, pp. 65–68, doi: 10.1109/ICITISEE.2018.8720966.
- [60] S. Geng, K. M. Y. Law, and B. Niu, "Investigating self-directed learning and technology readiness in blending learning environment," *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, vol. 16, no. 17, pp. 1–22, 2019, doi: 10.1186/s41239-019-0147-0.
- [61] H. Hafiar, "Blind media technology interface: Hoax checking based on applications and websites for the visually impaired," *ARNP Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, vol. 15, no. 10, pp. 1210–1217, 2020.
- [62] A. Abdullah, "The role of bandung local televisions in preventing the spread of hoax or fake news on social media," *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, vol. 8, no. 9, pp. 935–938, 2019.
- [63] K. Park, "'Click First!': The effects of instant activism via a hoax on social media," *Social Media and Society*, vol. 6, no. 2, 2020, doi: 10.1177/2056305120904706.
- [64] Y. Mejova, "Special Issue on Disinformation, hoaxes and propaganda within online social networks and media," *Online Social Networks and Media*, vol. 23, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.osnem.2021.100132.
- [65] W. H. Utomo, "Hoax classification corona virus (COVID-19) news in Indonesian using the support vector machine (SVM) method," *Journal of Computer Science*, vol. 17, no. 8, pp. 692–708, 2021, doi: 10.3844/jcssp.2021.692.708.
- [66] A. Abdullah, "Indonesian local televisions obstacles in combating hoaxes in social-media," *Review of International Geographical Education Online*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 1175–1183, 2021, doi: 10.33403/rigeo.8006833.

- [67] R. Pakpahan, "Analysis of the hoax phenomenon in various social media and how to deal with hoaxes," *Konferensi Nasional Ilmu Sosial dan Teknologi (KNiST)*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 479–484, 2017.
- [68] E. H. Susanto, "Social media, hoax, and threats against diversity in Indonesia," *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, vol. 8, no. 12, pp. 328–344, 2019.
- [69] A. Prasetyo, "Evaluation of feature extraction TF-IDF in Indonesian hoax news classification," *Proceedings - 2019 International Seminar on Application for Technology of Information and Communication: Industry 4.0: Retrospect, Prospect, and Challenges, iSemantic 2019*, 2019, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/ISEMANTIC.2019.8884291.
- [70] J. Pérez-Seoane, "Institutional advertising in the face of COVID-19 hoaxes: strategies, messages and narratives in the Spanish case," *Smart Innovation, Systems and Technologies*, vol. 259, pp. 249–258, 2022, doi: 10.1007/978-981-16-5792-4_25.
- [71] M. Constantinou, "I won't comply because it is a hoax: Conspiracy beliefs, lockdown compliance, and the importance of psychological flexibility," *Journal of Contextual Behavioral Science*, vol. 20, pp. 46–51, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jcbs.2021.03.001.
- [72] C. Moreno-Castro, "Exploratory study of the hoaxes spread via WhatsApp in Spain to prevent and/or cure COVID-19," *Gaceta Sanitaria*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 534–541, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.gaceta.2020.07.008.
- [73] R. K. Kaliyar, "Classification of hoax/non-hoax news articles on social media using an effective deep neural network," *Proceedings - 5th International Conference on Computing Methodologies and Communication, ICCMC 2021*, 2021, pp. 935–941, doi: 10.1109/ICCMC51019.2021.9418282.
- [74] I. M. A. F. I. M. Akbar, "Classification hoax news of covid-19 on Instagram using k-nearest neighbor," *10th IEEE International Conference on Communication, Networks and Satellite, Comnetsat 2021 - Proceedings*, pp. 157–161, 2021, doi: 10.1109/COMNETSAT53002.2021.9530828.
- [75] Y. D. Astuti, "Digital literacy competence of Indonesian lecturers on analysis hoax in social media," *Library Philosophy and Practice*, vol. 2021, 2021.
- [76] S. Tasnim, M. Hossain, and H. Mazumder, "Impact of rumors and misinformation on covid-19 in social media," *Journal of Preventive Medicine and Public Health*, vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 171–174, 2020, doi: 10.3961/JPMMPH.20.094.
- [77] X. López-García, "Journalistic fact-checking of information in pandemic: Stakeholders, hoaxes, and strategies to fight disinformation during the covid-19 crisis in Spain," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 1–15, 2021, doi: 10.3390/ijerph18031227.
- [78] A. Afdal et al., "An analysis of phubbing behaviour: preliminary research from counseling perspective," *Proceedings of the International Conference on Educational Sciences and Teacher Profession (ICETeP 2018)*, 2019, doi: 10.2991/icetep-18.2019.65.
- [79] O. D. Apuke and B. Omar, "Fake news and COVID-19: modelling the predictors of fake news sharing among social media users," *Telematics and Informatics*, vol. 56, p. 101475, 2021.
- [80] B. Zhong, Y. Huang, and Q. Liu, "Mental health toll from the coronavirus: Social media usage reveals Wuhan residents' depression and secondary trauma in the COVID-19 outbreak," *Computers in human behavior*, vol. 114, p. 106524, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.chb.2020.106524.
- [81] B. Sumintono and W. Widhiarso, *Rasch modeling application in educational assessment*. Trim Komunikata, 2015.
- [82] Irwanto, E. Rohaeti, E. Widjajanti, and Suyanta, "Students' science process skill and analytical thinking ability in chemistry learning," in *AIP Conference Proceedings*, 2017, vol. 1868, no. 1, p. 30001.
- [83] I. Puspita, I. Kaniawati, and I. R. Suwama, "Analysis of critical thinking skills on the topic of static fluid," in *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2017, vol. 895, no. 1, p. 12100.
- [84] S. Cottrell, *Critical thinking skills: Effective analysis, argument and reflection*. Macmillan International Higher Education, 2017.
- [85] S. Polesie et al., "Attitudes toward artificial intelligence within dermatopathology: an international online survey," *Frontiers in medicine*, vol. 7, p. 698, 2020.
- [86] X. Guan, L. Xie, W.-G. Shen, and T.-C. Huan, "Are you a tech-savvy person? Exploring factors influencing customers using self-service technology," *Technology in Society*, vol. 65, p. 101564, 2021.
- [87] F. Femenia-Serra, J. F. Perles-Ribes, and J. A. Ivars-Baidal, "Smart destinations and tech-savvy millennial tourists: hype versus reality," *Tourism Review*, vol. 74, no. 1, pp. 63–81, 2019, doi: 10.1108/TR-02-2018-0018.
- [88] A. G. Renatovna and A. S. Renatovna, "Pedagogical and psychological conditions of preparing students for social relations on the basis of the development of critical thinking," *Psychology and Education Journal*, vol. 58, no. 2, pp. 4889–4902, 2021.
- [89] N. S. Ismail, J. Harun, M. A. Z. M. Zakaria, and S. M. Salleh, "The effect of Mobile problem-based learning application DicScience PBL on students' critical thinking," *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, vol. 28, pp. 177–195, 2018.
- [90] H. J. Duda, H. Susilo, and P. Newcombe, "Enhancing different ethnicity science process skills: Problem-based learning through practicum and authentic assessment," *International Journal of Instruction*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 1207–1222, 2019.
- [91] A. Muhlisin, "Reading, mind mapping, and sharing (RMS): Innovation of new learning model on science lecture to improve understanding concepts," *Journal for the Education of Gifted Young Scientists*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 323–340, 2019.
- [92] A. B. Prasetijo, "Hoax detection system on Indonesian news sites based on text classification using SVM and SGD," *Proceedings - 2017 4th International Conference on Information Technology, Computer, and Electrical Engineering, ICITACEE 2017*, vol. 2018, 2017, pp. 45–49, doi: 10.1109/ICITACEE.2017.8257673.
- [93] J. A. Braun, "Fake news, real money: ad tech platforms, profit-driven hoaxes, and the business of journalism," *Digital Journalism*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–21, 2019, doi: 10.1080/21670811.2018.1556314.
- [94] N. Klimova, "Development of critical thinking in education: A case study on hoax messages," *ICETA 2019 - 17th IEEE International Conference on Emerging eLearning Technologies and Applications, Proceedings*, 2019, pp. 396–402, doi: 10.1109/ICETA48886.2019.9040087.
- [95] S. Y. Yuliani, "A framework for hoax news detection and analyzer used rule-based methods," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 10, no. 10, pp. 402–408, 2019, doi: 10.14569/ijacsa.2019.0101055.
- [96] C. Siregar, "Pancasila, ethos respect, and anti-hoaxes on internet-based social media," *PervasiveHealth: Pervasive Computing Technologies for Healthcare*, pp. 3–7, 2019, doi: 10.1145/3348445.3348446.
- [97] W. Nellen, "Just a minute: A hoax, a conceptual penis and the consequences," *Biologie in Unserer Zeit*, vol. 47, no. 4, p. 227, 2017, doi: 10.1002/biuz.201770414.
- [98] C. S. Ho, C. Y. Chee, and R. C. Ho, "Mental health strategies to combat the psychological impact of covid-19 beyond paranoia and panic," *Annals of the Academy of Medicine of Singapore*, vol. 49, no. 3, pp. 155–160, 2020.
- [99] C. V. Baccarella, T. F. Wagner, J. H. Kietzmann, and I. P. McCarthy, "Social media? It's serious! Understanding the dark side of social media," *European Management Journal*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 431–438, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.emj.2018.07.002.
- [100] L. S. Nowell, J. M. Norris, D. E. White, and N. J. Moules, "Thematic analysis: Striving to meet the trustworthiness criteria," *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 1–13, 2017, doi: 10.1177/1609406917733847.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Afdal is an Associate Professor and Lecturer at Study Program Guidance and Counseling Universitas Negeri Padang. He was appointed lecturer in the university since 2008. He has been a lecturer at the Department of Guidance and FIP UNP. As a scientist and researcher, he often received research grants, both from UNP and from the ministry. Research topics that are usually carried out are related to Domestic Violence, Marriage Counseling, Careers and Counseling in various special populations. He is the founder of the Research Center for Adolescent and Family Development (RC-AFD) and member of Cyberpsychology Intervention and Research Center Universitas Negeri Padang since 2021. Apart from being a researcher, he has also been entrusted with the Coordinator of the Counselor Professional Education Study Program since 2018-2019. Currently serving as Secretary of the BK FIP UNP Department since 2019. He can be contacted at email: afdal@konselor.org, afdal.kons@fip.unp.ac.id.

Miftahul Fikri is a Doctoral Candidate, Study Program Guidance and Counseling, Universitas Negeri Padang. He has been a lecturer assistant, research assistant for lecturer research projects at UNP and has published several articles in reputable national and international journals. Research topics and scientific studies that are usually carried out are related to counseling for special populations, domestic violence, social anxiety in prisoners and family counseling. He can be contacted at email: fikri@konselor.org.

Neviyarni is Professor and Lecturer at Study Program Guidance and Counseling Universitas Negeri Padang. She has more than 20 years of experience as an Academician at Universitas Negeri Padang, where she currently serves as Professor and Head of the Masters and Doctoral Guidance and Counseling Study Programs at the Faculty of Education. Her current research interests include student learning and development at various levels and areas of education. The topics of publication are social, education, guidance and counseling, education, learning strategies. She can be contacted at: neviyarni.suhaili911@gmail.com.

Mega Iswari is Professor and Lecturer at Special Education Universitas Negeri Padang. She has more than 20 years of experience as an Academician at Padang State University, where he currently serves as Professor Special Education and Head GPMI (*Gugus Penjamin Mutu Internal* --Internal Quality Assurance) FIP UNP. Her current research interests include student learning and development at various levels and areas of education. The topics of publication are social, education, guidance and counseling, special education. She can be contacted at email: mega_iswari@yahoo.com.

Indah Sukmawati is Lecturer at Study Program Guidance and Counseling Universitas Negeri Padang. She was appointed lecturer in the university since 2008. The focus of research and publications is on Family Counseling, Domestic Violence and Marriage Counseling. Active in research and learning activities at UNP and has published several articles in accredited national journals and proceedings. She can be contacted at email: i.watsan@yahoo.com.

Firman is Professor and Lecturer at Guidance and Counseling Universitas Negeri Padang. He has more than 20 years of experience as an Academician at Padang State University, where he currently serves as Professor Guidance and Counseling and he is active has been Head Department Study Program Guidance and Counseling FIP UNP. He current research interests include student learning and development at various levels and areas of education. The topics of publication are social, education, guidance and counseling, culture social, sociology anthropology. He can be contacted at email: firman@konselor.org.

Yeni Karneli is an Associate Professor and Lecturer at Study Program Guidance and Counseling Universitas Negeri Padang. She was appointed lecturer in the university since 1986. She has been a lecturer at the Department of Guidance and FIP UNP. She is active has been entrusted with the Coordinator of the Counselor Professional Education Study Program since 2020. She can be contacted at email: yenikarneli.unp@gmail.com.

Mardianto is an Assistant Professor and Lecturer at Psychology at Faculty Psychology and Health, Universitas Negeri Padang. He was appointed lecturer in the university since 2006. His research on Social Psychology and Cyber Aggression led him to become the Chair of the Cyberpsychology Intervention and Research Center Universitas Negeri Padang since 2021. He currently serves as Deputy Dean III (Student and Alumni Affairs) Faculty of Psychology and Health, Universitas Negeri Padang. He can be contacted at email: mardiantopsi@fip.unp.ac.id

Rezki Hariko is a Lecturer at Guidance and Counseling Department, Faculty of Education, Universitas Negeri Padang. He was appointed lecturer in the university since 2014. His research on group, adolescent and positive psychology. He is member of Cyberpsychology Intervention and Research Center Universitas Negeri Padang since 2021. He can be contacted at email: hariko.r@fip.unp.ac.id